

TACKLING FOOD INSECURITY THROUGH DIFFERENT MODELS OF COMMUNITY SUPPORT

National policy briefing in response to the UK Food Security Report 2024

We are a collaboration of people working on an NIHR-funded study to explore the roles community food organisations (CFOs) play in supporting families with children who have experienced food insecurity. We welcome the most recent [UK Food Insecurity Report](#), though argue that there is still more to consider given the key role CFOs play in both the food and welfare systems. Our research has observed a volatile sector with changing demand throughout the year, as well as increasing provision in both food and additional support. Data from CFO networks estimate over 6,300 CFOs throughout the UK, with levels of food support access far higher. This highlights the need for broader policy change and action at a national and local level.

Briefing purpose

This briefing highlights findings from our research with community food organisations and experts working across the UK. It provides recommendations for policymakers and any other interested parties in addressing food insecurity in families at a national level. This briefing is particularly relevant for the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, especially in developing a new Food Security Strategy, as well as the Department for Work and Pensions and the Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government. It is also intended to inform national policy on addressing poverty more broadly, including the government's Child Poverty Strategy. Our recommendations for local authorities have been published separately in a [local policy briefing and report](#).

National Policy recommendations (detailed in full below)

1. Reform the national welfare system to enable the government to achieve national food security and end mass dependence on food parcels (two key goals laid out in the Labour Party's manifesto).
2. Ensure that everyone in the UK, whether in work or not, receives a Living Income, as food insecurity is experienced by people in work as well as those receiving welfare benefit support.
3. Reform local welfare support to remove the patchwork of provision across the UK. This plays an important role in reducing and even preventing the need for food support.

What we did

Data were gathered from interviews and 5 workshops run between October 2023 and April 2024. We interviewed representatives from 36 organisations, including regional and national networks. Most representatives worked in food distribution, delivery of food support and related services; some were involved in capacity building support to CFOs and/or policy, research and campaigning work on food insecurity. Two workshops were held with 45 representatives from CFOs and partner organisations in two locations: Bradford and Tower Hamlets, and three additional workshops were held online with 22 representatives from local and national organisations. Data were analysed to explore models and components of CFOs and the interdependencies with social and economic systems in which they operate.

What we found

While CFOs provide a range of activities and services of value to communities, our research points to a series of significant sustainability challenges, alongside a need for broader policy change and action within and outside of the scope of the CFO sector.

- **CFOs are a key, but fragmented, component of both the food and welfare systems on which a growing number of families rely**

The sector is diverse, including different models of food support, such as food banks, pantries, community cafes and co-operatives in a range of settings, as well as differences in approaches, aims, services and activities. Many, but not all, operate as part of a wider network, which influences (a) the nature of food supply, (b) whether CFOs operate through referral pathways, (c) the availability of co-located additional (welfare) support and d) aims and objectives.

- **CFOs have seen dramatic growth and organisational change in the last 10 years - largely in response to the cost of living crisis and an inadequate welfare system**

Our evidence supports previous work that highlights how insufficient levels of income support for families, both at a national and local level (through Universal Credit and local discretionary support) has contributed to demand for food support. The sector has grown rapidly and become more differentiated. Emergency responses have increased alongside new approaches focusing on prevention, sustainability and/or food choice.

- **The demand for surplus food has increased along with the activities of food redistributors, while some CFOs are exploring alternative support and activities**

Low-cost trading models, such as pantries, have grown swiftly, while some CFO networks advocate for direct cash payments to families facing hardship (cash-first approaches). Some CFOs have expanded additional support including social welfare advice, via co-located support, referrals or signposting. Campaigning and policy work at a local and national level has also expanded among CFO networks.

- **All CFOs face a number of challenges**

The greatest challenge faced by CFOs in our research was in meeting a continued rise in the need for food support, linked to a broader rise in destitution, high rates of poverty and increases in the cost of living. This challenge was accompanied by dwindling levels of surplus food and donations, leading many CFOs to purchase food, bringing with it significant financial implications. This sits alongside broader challenges in maintaining organisational sustainability, a reliance on volunteers, as well as unpredictable and limited funding. CFOs face further dilemmas in the extent to which, by design or practice, their role becomes embedded or entrenched, while wider local and national services lack the capacity to prevent food insecurity.

Policy priorities in full

1. Reform the national welfare system

- Remove arbitrary payment caps including the Benefit Cap and the Two Child Limit.
- End sanctions and deductions applied to Universal Credit (UC) recipients, as well as delays to receiving support, such as the five-week wait for UC.
- Ensure that the level of income people receive enables recipients to meet the cost of living, as a minimum.

2. Real living wages and security in work

- Uprate the current National Living Wage in line with the Real Living Wage (RLW), as set by the [Living Wage Foundation](#).
- Ensure that the [New Deal for Working People](#) delivers on commitments to achieve a transformative change to job security and employment rights.
- Support local authorities to include payment of the RLW by employers in strategies to address and prevent food insecurity.
- Commit to ensuring everyone in the UK, whether in work or not, receives at least a Living Income, a level that guarantees the ability to meet the cost of living.

3. Reform local welfare support

a. The government and devolved administrations should:

- Provide sustainable funding to local authorities to address the impact of austerity on local welfare support.
- Ensure funding for local welfare assistance is in-line with need and claimants can access support, through:
 - i) a long-term funding settlement to local authorities; ii) a review of local welfare assistance schemes; iii) a new national strategy for local welfare support.
- Prioritise direct cash provision within discretionary support policy guidance to local authorities.
- Ensure social welfare advice services are sustainably funded to ensure access to income support and related services.
- Remove local welfare assistance and emergency support from the list of public funds, to ensure people with no recourse to public funds can access support.

b. The government and devolved administrations should support local authorities to ensure local welfare support services and referral pathways are coordinated to address and prevent food insecurity.

Conclusion

There is an urgent need for action to address the scale of poverty in the UK. National and local government plays a key role in this, especially to support household incomes. Without such action, the challenges noted above and the dilemmas faced by CFOs in seeking to support ever-rising levels of need, are unlikely to be addressed, while levels of food insecurity and poverty are likely to continue to rise.

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Further information

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